

Chemistry of lapachol – Syntheses of some new biogenetically related naphthoquinones, naphthoquinone dimers, naphthaquinoxaline and naphthaazaquinoxaline derivatives from lapachol[†]

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Abstract : The present short review focus on chemical transformations of lapachol to a large number of biogenetically related lapachol congeners, dimers and heterocyclic analogues that have been achieved in our laboratory during more than two decades. Conversion of lapachol to stenocarpoquinone-B, rhinacanthin-A, β -(1-hydroxyisopropanyl)-dihydrofurano-1,2-naphthoquinone, stenocarpoquinone-A, dehydro- α -lapachone and dehydro- β -lapachone by the reaction with *m*-chloroperbenzoic acid; dehydroiso- α -lapachone, dehydroiso- β -lapachone, dehydro- α -lapachone, α -lapachone and β -lapachone by the reaction with aqueous NaNO₂ and glacial AcOH; adenophyllone, quadrilone and dehydro- α -lapachone by the reaction with boiling pyridine; naphthaquinoxaline and naphthaazaquinoxaline derivatives by the reaction with 1,2-diamines and dialkyltin dilapacholates by the reaction with dialkyltin diisopropoxides have been accomplished. Notably the syntheses of rhinacanthin-A, β -(1-hydroxyisopropanyl)-dihydrofurano-1,2-naphthoquinone, dehydroiso- α -lapachone, dehydroiso- β -lapachone, adenophyllone and quadrilone have been reported for the first time from our group starting from lapachol. The synthesis of novel naphthaquinoxaline and azaquinoxaline derivatives from lapachol has been additional interesting results of this investigation.

Keywords : Lapachol, lapachol congeners, rhinacanthin-A, adenophyllone, quadrilone, naphthaquinoxaline and azaquinoxaline derivatives.

Introduction

Quinones are naturally occurring plant pigments and are being found in plants, fungi, bacteria, arthropods and echinoderm^{1,2}. These are commercially used as natural dyes in pharmaceutical, cosmetic and textile industries³. Their molecular structures endow them with redox properties, which confer activity in various biological oxidative processes. The toxicity and therapeutic activities of quinones involve the formation of reactive oxygen species⁴⁻⁶. The biological redox cycle of quinones can be initiated by one electron reduction leading to the formation of semiquinones, unstable intermediates that react sharply with molecular oxygen generating free radicals. Since the pioneering work of Wendel⁷ in 1946, who exhibited that certain naphthoquinones inhibit the growth of *Plasmodium vivax* and the work of Fieser *et al.* in the 1940's an extensive search for new quinones for use in

malaria treatment has started⁸. A large number of quinones have been tried for their antitumor⁹, trypanocidal¹⁰, molluscicidal¹¹, leishmanicidal¹², anti-inflammatory¹³ and antifungal¹⁴ activities.

The most important naphthoquinone is lapachol (2-hydroxy-3-(3-methyl-2-butenyl)-1,4-naphthoquinone) 1, a versatile biological active compound isolated from the heartwood of *Tecomella undulata*¹⁵ (Bignoniaceae).

It is clearly visible with naked eyes in the heartwood shavings of above plant as yellow granules. It is also

[†]In honour of Professor Jai P. Mittal.

extracted from the heartwood of several plants of family Bignoniaceae¹⁶⁻¹⁹, Malvaceae²⁰, Verbenaceae²¹, etc. One important structural feature of its chemical reactivity is the cyclization of prenyl side chain leading to α - and β -lapachones originally obtained as side products during the isolation of lapachol.

Lapachol is used against Chagas disease and as a neoplastic agent^{22,23}. Antimetastatic action of lapachol on B 16 melanoma, at low dosage (5–20 mg/kg) is observed through an unknown mechanism, where as a high toxic dose of lapachol promotes metastasis by inducing a hypercoagulable state as a result of vitamin K-dependent pathway inhibition²⁴. A number of synthetic derivatives of lapachol, such as mono-(arylimines)-*o*-quinones derived from β -lapachone, have shown cytotoxicity against human cancer cells²⁵ and tricyclic furano- and pyrano-1,4-naphthoquinone derivatives have displayed potent cytotoxicity against cell lines derived from human tumors (A-549, MCF-7, HT-29)^{25,26}. Several other naphthoquinones related to lapachol have been shown to exhibit a notable cancer preventive potential²⁷⁻²⁹. Lapachol patents having medical applications have been increasing and there were 13 patents in 2008³⁰ alone.

Another very important biological active naphthoquinone is β -lapachone (3,4-dihydro-2,2-dimethyl-2*H*-naphtho[1,2-*b*]pyran-5,6-dione) **2** also isolated along with lapachol from the heartwood of *Tecomella undulata*¹⁵. Literature survey revealed that β -lapachone can directly target DNA topoisomerases and inhibits their activity, which results in cytotoxicity³¹. Its mechanism of action is quite distinct from that of other typical topoisomerase

inhibitors, viz. camptothecin and its analogues³¹. Due to the synergistic effect of β -lapachone **2** with taxol against several tumor cell lines has been a new approach in cancer therapy³². In addition, β -lapachone also possesses a number of pharmacological effects including anti-bacterial, antifungal, trypanocidal and cytotoxic activities, which are linked to the formation of reactive oxygen species³¹.

Thus central feature of 1,2- and 1,4-quinonoid based cytotoxins is their ability to generate semiquinone radicals by bioreduction, which then accelerate intramolecular hypoxic conditions^{33,34}.

Previous work

Earlier transformation studies of lapachol **1** include its conversion to β -lapachone **2** when lapachol is dissolved in concentrated sulphuric acid and then poured into water or by treating **1** with anhydrous AlCl_3 and α -lapachone **3** when lapachol is treated with hydrochloric acid (in acetic acid). Both isomers β -lapachone **2** and α -lapachone **3** are formed when lapachol is dissolved in concentrated nitric acid. Further, concentrated sulphuric acid converts α -lapachone into β -isomer and the process is reversed in concentrated hydrochloric acid³⁵. The transformation of lapachol into dehydro- α -lapachone **4** is achieved by treating with pyridine³⁵ (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

Results and discussion

As part of a programme concerned with the chemical cyclization of lapachol our group has been engaged during the over last two decades in this endeavour. Reaction of lapachol **1** with *meta*-chloroperbenzoic acid in methylene chloride for 30 min at 0 °C resulted in the formation of stenocarpoquinone- β **5**, β -(1-hydroxyisopropanyl)-dihydrofurano-1,2-naphthoquinone **6**, rhinacanthin-A **7** and stenocarpoquinone-A **8**. When the reaction was extended for four hours and at 25 °C, dehydration of **7** and **8** led to the formation of dehydro- α -lapachone **4** and dehydro- β -lapachone **9**³⁶, respectively (Scheme 2).

Scheme 2

Probable mechanism of formation of products **5-8** proceeds through the initial formation of tautomeric epoxides^{37,38} (**1a**) and (**1b**). Alternate epoxy ring opening and subsequent cyclization may then afford both dihydrofurano naphthoquinones **5** and **6** and dihydropyrano naphthoquinones **7** and **8**³⁶ (Scheme 3).

Rhinacanthin-A **7**, a new naturally occurring 1,4-naphthoquinone, has been reported from the plant *Rhinacanthus nasutus* (Acanthaceae)³⁹. So it is the first synthesis of rhinacanthin-A **7** along with β -(1-hydroxyisopropanyl)-dihydrofurano-1,2-naphthoquinone **6** and dehydro- β -lapachone **9** from lapachol³⁶. Stenocarpoquinone-A and -B were previously isolated from the wood of *Stenocarpus salignus* (Proteaceae)³⁷. Their synthesis

was also reported from lapachol by the reaction with *m*-chloroperbenzoic acid^{37,38} or peracetic acid⁴⁰.

When lapachol **1** was allowed to react with HNO₂ generated *in situ* by the reaction of aqueous NaNO₂ and glacial AcOH dehydroiso- α -lapachone **10**, dehydroiso- β -lapachone **11**, β -lapachone **2**, α -lapachone **3**, and dehydro- α -lapachone **4**, were obtained⁴¹. The formation of 2-hydroxy-3-(2,3-dibromo-3-methylbutyl)-1,4-naphthoquinone **12** and 2-hydroxy-3-(2,3-dibromo-3-methylbutyl)-6-bromo-1,4-naphthoquinone **13** was achieved by the reaction of **1** with bromine in chloroform⁴¹ (Scheme 4).

Dehydroiso- α -lapachone **10**, a natural dihydrofurano-1,4-naphthoquinone was previously reported from the woods of *Paratecoma peroba*⁴², *Tabebuia pentaphylla*⁴³, *Radermachera sinica*⁴⁴ and also by our group from the heartwoods of *Tabebuia rosea*¹⁶ and *Markhamia platycalyx*¹⁸ (all Bignoniaceae). The occurrence of dehydroiso- β -lapachone **11** has not yet reported from nature. It is the first report of the synthesis of these two dehydroiso isomers **10** and **11** starting from lapachol⁴¹.

The compounds **10** and **11** were obtained as major products in the above reaction and their formation can be rationalized by addition of acetic acid to olefinic double bond of the side chain of lapachol. Subsequent removal of one of the methylene hydrogens as hydride ion, though

Scheme 3

Scheme 4

energetically not favourable but the stability of products leading to cyclization to the five membered ring which on elimination of AcOH gave compounds 10 and 11. The formation of α -lapachone and its β -isomer (3 and 2) can be explained by considering the decomposition of nitrous acid to nitric acid under refluxing condition and latter transformed 1 into α - and β -lapachones in equal quantity for which there is precedent³⁵. The formation of sodium acetate during reaction and subsequent abstraction of one of the methylene protons by the nucleophilic attack of acetoxo ion resulted in the formation of dehydro- α -lapachone 4³⁷.

Lapachol 1 on refluxing with pyridine for 6 h resulted in the formation of red mass which on chromatographic separation gave quadrilone 14, dehydro- α -lapachone 4 and adenophyllone 15⁴⁵ respectively (Scheme 5).

Quadrilone (4-hydroxy-2,2-dimethyl-2H-3,9-dioxadibenzo[*a,de*]-naphthacene-10,15-dione) 14 was also simultaneously isolated as gray purple powder, m.p. 232 °C from the heartwood of *Heterophragma quadriloculare*⁴⁵ (Bignoniaceae) as naturally occurring pigment. Adenophyllone (4-hydroxy-2-methyl-2-[(1*E*)-4-methyl-penta-1,3-dienyl]-2H-3,9-dioxadibenzo[*a,de*]-naphthacene-10,15-dione) 15 was obtained as purple needles, m.p. 226–227 °C from the heartwood of *H. adenophyllum*⁴⁶. Different mechanisms for the formation of dehydro- α -lapachone 4 from lapachol were suggested by several authors in different medium and catalysts, involving oxidative cyclization between C-2 and C-3^{47–49}. In addition to the pyridine catalyzed formation of 4^{47–50} a modified Hooker oxidation in presence of KMnO_4 resulted in the formation of 2-hydroxy-1,4-naphthoquinone 16 from

Scheme 5

lapachol⁵¹. Though the compound 16 could not be detected in reaction mixture, but the structure of quadrilone 14 is composed of substructures of those similar to 4 and 16 (Scheme 6). An oxidative coupling between a quinone radical of 16 (IV) with hydroquinone form of 4 (V) may

produce quadrilone 14, after dehydration and dehydrogenation of the resulting adduct (Scheme 6)⁵². Possible mechanism of the formation of adenophyllone 15 from 14, a prenyl group in II and III may be subjected to a nucleophilic attack by VII (Scheme 7). The resulting alkyl

Scheme 6. Suggested mechanism for the formation of quadrilone 14. The nucleophile may be pyridine or a conjugated base of a hydroxy naphthoquinone.

Scheme 7. Suggested mechanism for the formation of adenophyllone 15.

side chain may be oxidized at newly formed allylic position, followed by dehydration to form **15** (Scheme 7). The mechanism of the formation of **VI** in an auto-oxidative ring opening was suggested for **4** previously⁴⁸. The above mechanisms of the formation of **14** and **15** were suggested according to the mechanistic investigation on related compounds^{47-49,52-55}. However to confirm the mechanisms of these transformations more detailed investigations seem to be essential.

β -Lapachone **2**, a 1,2-naphthoquinone is obtained in low yield naturally and was synthesized from lapachol through angular cyclization of isoprenyl side chain of lapachol with conc. H_2SO_4 . The reaction of β -lapachone **2** with 1,2-diaminoethane at room temperature gave a novel tetracyclic pyrazine derivative **16** (Scheme 8). This observation is in contrast to what Di Chenna *et al.* observed²⁵. We have not obtained monoarylimine-*o*-quinone derivative. We have further extended our studies to the reaction of β -lapachone with 1,2-diaminopropane at room temperature. A pair of regioisomers **17** and **18** were formed in a ratio of 2 : 3 as novel tetracyclic pyrazines. These were characterized as 5,6-dihydro-2,7,7-trimethyl-7H-pyrano[3',2':4]naphtha[1,2-*b*]pyrazine **17** and 5,6-dihydro-3,7,7-trimethyl-7H-pyrano[3',2':4]naphtha[1,2-*b*]pyrazine **18** respectively (Scheme 8).

Scheme 8

The structure of pyrazine derivative **16** involving facile dehydrogenative cyclocondensation even under mild conditions was confirmed by single crystal X-ray diffraction and is characterized as 5,6-dihydro-7,7-dimethyl-7H-pyrano-[3',2':4]naphtha[1,2-*b*]pyrazine⁵⁶ (Fig. 1).

Molecular structure of 5,6-dihydro-7,7-dimethyl-7H-pyrano[3',2':4]naphtha[1,2-*b*]pyrazine **16**

Compound **16**, which crystallizes in the space group orthorhombic, Pnma, is displayed in the ORTEP diagram

Fig. 1. ORTEP plot of $C_{17}H_{16}N_2O$.

(Fig. 1). The values of bond lengths 1.402 (7) Å for C(1)-C(2), 1.362 (8) Å for C(3)-C(4), 1.338 (7) Å for C(1)-N(2), 1.331 (8) Å for N(2)-C(4), 1.323 (7) Å for N(1)-C(3) and 1.365 (7) Å for N(1)-C(2) were consistent with the aromatization of the ring, confirming the formation of **16**.

The reaction of lapachol **1** with *o*-phenylene diamine

gave 9,9-dimethyl-9H-pyrano[3',2':4]naphtha[1,2-*b*]quinoxaline **19** (Scheme 9), representing a new entry into the synthesis of heterocyclic compounds from hydroxylated naphthoquinones. The reaction of lapachol **1** with 2,3-diaminopyridine under MW irradiation occurred regioselectively giving only one product namely 8,8-dimethyl-8H-pyrano[3',2':4]naphtha[1,2-*e*]pyrido[2,3-*b*]pyrazine **21** (Scheme 9), while reaction was unsuccessful under conventional thermal condition. The synthesis of

product 20 has been carried out by the two process (i) by the hydrogenation of product 19, (ii) by reaction of β -lapachone 2 with *o*-phenylene diamine in ethanol at room temperature.

Molecular structure of 6,7-dihydro-8,8-dimethyl-8H-pyrano[3',2':4]naphtha[2,1-e]pyrido[2,3-b]pyrazine 22b

Compound 22b, which crystallizes in the space group

Scheme 9

Reaction of β -lapachone 2 with 2,3-diaminopyridine by conventional heating led to the formation of a pair of regioisomers (azaquinoxaline derivatives 22a and 22b) in 3 : 1 ratio indicating the regioselectivity in the process. Regioselectivity in the reaction confirmed by taking single crystal X-ray diffraction of 22b (Fig. 2) and it is identified as 6,7-dihydro-8,8-dimethyl-8H-pyrano[3',2':4]-naphtha[2,1-e]pyrido[2,3-b]pyrazine⁵⁷.

Pbca, is displayed in the ORTEP diagram (Fig. 2). The values of bond lengths 1.484 (8) Å for C(8)-C(9), 1.399 (9) Å for C(14)-C(15), 1.316 (7) Å for N(1)-C(9), 1.385 (8) Å for N(1)-C(15), 1.300 (7) Å for N(2)-C(8) and 1.368 (7) Å for N(2)-C(14) were consistent with the aromatization of the ring, confirming the formation of 22b.

The major isomer 22a is probably arisen from the attack by more nucleophilic amino group at position-3 in 2,3-diaminopyridine^{58,59} on the more electrophilic 1-carbonyl function of 1,2-quinonoid form of lapachol 1a (Scheme 10). There are several reports in the literature^{55,60} indicating that the carbonyl nearest to the aromatic ring is more reactive than 2-carbonyl group in *o*-quinonoid form of lapachol or β -lapachone.

Hydroxy naphthoquinones and their chelation with various metal ions alter their activity tremendously. For instance organotin(IV) complexes of juglone displayed more antibacterial activity than the free ligands⁶¹. Thus their chelating ability plays an important role and the study of their metal chelates has been of great interest in understanding mechanisms of their chemical and biological activities. Chelating property of lapachol 1 may slow its delivery and so potentially be able to modulate and/or

Fig. 2. ORTEP plot of the asymmetric unit of $C_{20}H_{17}N_3O$.

Scheme 10

improve its therapeutic activity. Recently coordination complexes of lapachol **1** with zinc, cobalt and manganese(II) have been reported⁶²⁻⁶⁴. The organotin(IV) chelates of lapachol (**23**) were synthesized by the reaction of dimethyltin, di-*n*-butyltin and diphenyltin diisopropoxides with lapachol⁶⁵ (Scheme 11). Due to the highly oxidizable and extremely hydrolysable nature of organotin alkoxides, all the reactions were carried out under dry nitrogen. All the reagents were dried and purified by the standard methods.

Scheme 11

Experimental

Qualitative and quantitative thin layer chromatography were conducted on TLC aluminium sheets kieselgel 60F₂₅₄ (E. Merck). ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR spectra were recorded on JEOL AL 300 MHz FT NMR instrument using CDCl₃ as solvent. Mass spectra (FAB MS) were generated on a JEOL SX-102 spectrometer. Melting points were determined in soft glass capillaries in an electrothermal melting point apparatus and are uncorrected. Infrared spectra were recorded on FT IR 8400S spectrometer. All compounds were homogeneous on TLC in various solvent systems. Microwave assisted reactions were carried out in a multimode MW oven (Panasonic-NN-781JF) using ethanol as solvent or using different

solid supports such as neutral alumina, acidic alumina or basic alumina.

Lapachol, bright yellow needles, m.p. 139–140 °C and β-lapachone, orange red needles, m.p. 154–155 °C, isolated from the heartwood of *Tecomella undulata*¹⁵ (Bignoniaceae) were used for these reactions. Further amount of β-lapachone required for reactions was also prepared from lapachol by dissolving it in concentrated sulphuric acid.

(1) Reaction of lapachol **1** with *meta*-chloroperbenzoic acid

To a solution of lapachol **1** (2.4 g, 10 mmol) in dry dichloromethane (30 mL) was added to a solution of *m*-chloroperbenzoic acid (5.1 g, 30 mmol) in dichloromethane (50 mL) at 0 °C. After 30 min workup was carried out by treating the reaction mixture with a saturated aqueous sodium hydrogen sulphite (100 mL) for 20 min. The organic layer was separated, washed successively with saturated aqueous sodium bicarbonate (2 × 25 mL), water (2 × 25 mL) and dried over anhydrous MgSO₄. The crude orange solid 1.5 g was subjected to column chromatography over silica gel employing chloroform as a solvent. The products from various fractions were characterized as stenocarpoquinone-B **5**, yellow needles, 0.21 g, m.p. 160–161 °C, β-(1-hydroxyisopropanyl)-dihydrofuran-1,2-naphthoquinone **6**, red needles, 0.26 g m.p. 132 °C, rhinacanthin **7**, orange solid, 0.1 g, m.p. 170–171 °C. When the reaction was carried out at 25 °C for a period of 4 h dehydro-α-lapachone **4**, orange needles, 0.035 g, m.p. 143–144 °C and dehydro-β-lapachone **9**, as red solid, 0.020 g were obtained in addition to above compounds.

(2) Reaction of lapachol **1** with HNO₂

To a solution of lapachol **1** (2.0 g, 8.3 mmol) in glacial acetic acid (100 mL) in 250 mL RB flask, an aqueous solution of NaNO₂ (3.208 g, 46 mmol) was added and the resulting mixture was heated at 80 °C for 6 h with magnetic stirring. It was left overnight and then reaction

mixture was diluted and extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was washed with 2% NaHCO₃ solution and water respectively. The ethereal layer was dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄ and subjected to preparative TLC on precoated glass plates giving dehydroiso- α -lapachone **10**, golden yellow leaflets, 0.070 g, m.p. 102–103 °C, dehydroiso- β -lapachone **11**, red granules, 0.065 g, m.p. 96 °C, β -lapachone **2**, red needles, 0.040 g, m.p. 154–155 °C, α -lapachone **3**, pale yellow needles, 0.050 g, m.p. 117–118 °C and dehydro- α -lapachone **4**, red needles, 0.045 g, m.p. 143–144 °C.

(3) Reaction of lapachol 1 with bromine

A solution of lapachol **1** (1.5 g, 6.2 mmol) in 90 mL of CHCl₃ in a stoppered conical flask was treated with a solution of bromine in CHCl₃ (4 mL of Br₂ dissolved in 15 mL of CHCl₃) and resulting mixture was heated for 5 min on a water-bath and kept overnight at room temperature. The excess Br₂ and chloroform was removed by evaporation in fuming cup-board. It was separated by prep. TLC using precoated glass plates with silica gel into 2-hydroxy-3-[2,3-dibromo-3-methylbutyl]-1,4-naphthoquinone **12** as violet red viscous mass, 0.075 g and 2-hydroxy-3-[2,3-dibromo-3-methylbutyl]-6-bromo-1,4-naphthoquinone **13** as maroon needles, 0.15 g, m.p. 168–169 °C.

(4) Reaction of lapachol 1 with pyridine

Lapachol **1** (3.0 g, 12.4 mmol) and dry pyridine (45 mL) were mixed together and refluxed for 6 h in a sand-bath at 210 °C. Resulting red mass was poured into ice-cold water (100 mL) and extracted with solvent ether (2 × 50 mL) and chloroform (2 × 50 mL). The chloroform extract was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and subjected to column chromatography over silica gel (60–120 mesh, Merck) on elution with petroleum ether-benzene (3 : 1) gave dehydro- α -lapachone **4**, as orange needles, 0.860 g, m.p. 143–144 °C, petroleum ether-benzene (1 : 1) yielded adenophyllone **15**, as gray purple needles, 0.300 g, m.p. 226–227 °C and pure benzene gave quadrilone **14**, as gray-purple powder, 0.190 g, m.p. 232 °C.

(5) Reaction β -lapachone 2 with aliphatic 1,2-diamines

β -Lapachone **2** (0.061 g, 0.25 mmol) and 1,2-diaminoethane (2 mL) were stirred at room temperature for 24 h. Petroleum ether (60–80 °C, 10 mL) was added to the reaction mixture. Crude product is separated by filtration and purified by prep. TLC to give **16** as yellow needles, 0.055 g, m.p. 77–80 °C. Analogous reaction of β -lapachone **2** with 1,2-diaminopropane was completed at room temperature in 5 min. Crude product showed the

presence of two products in a ratio of 1 : 3. These two products were separated by prep. TLC and characterized as regioisomers **17** and **18** (benzene, *R_f* 0.48, 0.36 respectively) on the basis of spectral studies. The regioisomer **17** was obtained as pale yellow needles, 0.014 g, m.p. 75–78 °C and regioisomer **18** was isolated as bright yellow needles, 0.043 g, m.p. 70–72 °C.

(6) Reaction of lapachol 1 with aromatic/heteroaromatic-1,2-diamines

The *o*-phenylenediamine (0.054 g, 0.50 mmol) was added to the solution of lapachol **1** (0.121 g, 0.50 mmol) in ethanol (20 mL) and reaction mixture was refluxed for 18 h. The progress of reaction was monitored on TLC plate which showed the formation of dark pink coloured product which was found to be unstable and converted into yellow coloured product with the passage of time. Resulting reaction mixture was purified by prep. TLC using petroleum ether-benzene (3 : 1) to give **19** as yellow needles, 0.60 g, m.p. 120–123 °C.

An equimolar (1 mmol) mixture of lapachol **1** and 2,3-diaminopyridine was refluxed for 3–4 days in ethanol. TLC indicated the unchanged reactants and no new product was formed. The reaction was carried out successfully under microwaves irradiation. An equimolar amount of lapachol (0.242 g, 1 mmol) and 2,3-diaminopyridine (0.109 g, 1 mmol) was absorbed on solid support (such as neutral, acidic and basic alumina) via a solution of ethanol. The dry free flowing powder was placed into a pyrex-glass opened vessel and irradiated in the microwave oven at 600 watt for 10 min. The reaction mixture was purified by prep. TLC using benzene-ethyl acetate (9 : 1, *R_f* 0.64) to give **21** as purple crystals, m.p. 110–112 °C.

(7) Reaction of β -lapachone 2 with aromatic/heteroaromatic-1,2-diamines

The reaction of β -lapachone **2** (0.242 g, 1 mmol) with *o*-phenylenediamine (0.108 g, 1 mmol) in ethanol at room temperature led to the formation of a single product. This product was purified by prep. TLC using benzene (*R_f* 0.76) **20**, as bright yellow needles, m.p. 113–115 °C. The conversion of **19** into **20** was carried out over palladium on charcoal (10%) using ethyl acetate as solvent. The reaction was run at room temperature and 50 psi under hydrogen pressure.

A solution of β -lapachone **2** (0.242 g, 1 mmol), 2,3-diaminopyridine (0.109 g, 1 mmol) in ethanol (30 mL) containing few drops of glacial acetic acid was refluxed for 24 h. The progress of reaction was monitored on

TLC plate and indicated the formation of two products. These products were separated by prep. TLC [benzene-ethyl acetate (9 : 1)] as **22a** and **22b** in the ratio of 3 : 1 respectively. But under MW irradiation the reaction showed the formation of isomers in the ratio of 3 : 2 indicating enhance yield of isomer **22a**.

(8) Reaction of lapachol 1 with diorganotin dialkoxides

To a solution of dialkyltin diisopropoxide in benzene was added a benzene solution of lapachol **1** in the stoichiometric ratio of 1 : 2. The reaction mixture was refluxed under a fractionating column at bath temperature and the liberated isopropanol was fractionated azeotropically over a period of 3–5 h. After complete removal of isopropanol the excess solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the resulting solid **23** were crystallized from benzene or benzene-hexane (1 : 1) mixture.

The identity of known compounds was established by direct comparison or by comparing their spectral data from literature. The structures of newly formed compounds were established with the help of modern spectral techniques (¹H, ¹³C, DEPT, 2D NMR, HMQC, HMBC and single crystal X-ray diffraction). Details of spectral data of these compounds are available in appropriate references cited in this article.

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